

Gender in Horizon projects

Consortia focusing on NBS, water treatment or both

In order to understand how gender is integrated into and perceived among project implementors, financed by the Horizon programme, research was conducted in October and November 2024 among the following 5 consortia: CARDIMED, NICE, MARCLAIMED, BOOST-IN, and NetworkNature. The consortia are financed by Horizon Europe and they focus on NBS, water treatment or both. Surveys were undertaken in three areas: gender representation, Gender equality plans (GEP) and gender mainstreaming.

Gender balance

O1

Everyone working by gender: 71,5 % W – 21,5 % M

Researchers by gender: 60 % W – 40 % M

Non-researchers by gender: 100 % W

Work package / task leaders by gender: 66 % W – 33 % M

O2

Everyone working by gender: 27 % W – 73 % M

Researchers by gender: 22 % W – 78 % M

Non-researchers by gender: 50 % W – 50 % M

Work package / task leaders by gender: gender disaggregated data NA

O3

Everyone working by gender: 100 % W

Researchers by gender: 0 %

Non-researchers by gender: 100 % W

Work package / task leaders by gender: 0 %

O4

Everyone working by gender: 25 % W – 75 % M

Researchers by gender: 100 % M

Non-researchers by gender: 33 % W – 66 % M

Work package / task leaders by gender: 100 % M

O5

Everyone working by gender: 47 % W – 53 % M

Researchers by gender: NA

Non-researchers by gender: NA

Work package / task leaders by gender: NA

O6

Everyone working by gender: 45 % W – 55 % M

Researchers by gender: 25 % W – 75 % M

Non-researchers by gender: 100 % W

Work package / task leaders by gender: 40 % W – 60 % M

O7

Everyone working by gender: 57 % W – 43 % M

Researchers by gender: 66 % W - 33 % M

Non-researchers by gender: 50 % W – 50 % M

Work package / task leaders by gender: 100 % M

Together (based on provided gender disaggregated data)

Everyone working by gender: 26 W – 24 M

Researchers by gender: 12 W – 19 M (39 % W – 61 % M)

Non-researchers by gender: 14 W – 5 M

Work package / task leaders by gender: (1 org did not provide GDD) 4 W – 6 M

Women represented 52 % of all employed, out of which 46 % were researchers and 54 % were non-researchers. Men represented 48 % of all employed, out of which 79 % worked as researchers and 21 % as non-researchers.

24 % of women worked as researchers and 28 % as non-researchers. 38 % men worked as researchers and 10 % as non-researchers.

Women led 40 % of the work/task leads, while men led 60 % of them.

Answers where gender analysis was not possible due to lack of provided gender disaggregated data:

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Gender equality plan

1. Does your entity have a GEP in place?

a) Yes IIIIIIIII

b) No III

2. Did your entity have a GEP in place before it became an eligibility criterion for Horizon calls for all public bodies, higher education institutions and research organisations?
 - c) yes II
 - d) no !!!!!!!

3. What was the reason for the adoption of the GEP?
 - a) the Horizon requirement
 - b) the recognised need for more gender equality within the entity I
 - c) both !!!!!
 - d) we don't need the GEP to apply to Horizon projects !!

4. When preparing the GEP, did your entity consult with any of the following actors / offices?
 - a) office / department within my entity dealing with gender and/or social justice issues !!!!!
 - b) trainings (online or live) provided by the EC or other actors on GEP II
 - c) external gender experts !!!!!
 - d) none of the above
 - e) not relevant (don't need GEP) !!

5. What kind of monitoring of the GEP has your entity carried out (there are more possible answers)?
 - a) yearly reports on the progress of GEP that include measurable indicators are published !!!!!
 - b) a gender equality coordinator meets periodically with the relevant team (human resources, office for gender / social justice, decision-makers etc) in order to assess the progress !!!!!
 - c) there are periodical trainings on gender equality available within my entity (gender balance at leadership levels, in recruitment and career progression, integration of gender dimension into research and teaching, work-life balance, gender-based violence) !!!!!
 - d) a general and brief chapter on gender is included in the yearly report of the entity !!!!!
 - e) none of the above. III

The organization that put in place a GEP previously to the Horizon requirement due to the recognized need for more GE within the organization had a very balanced gender representation, consulted also with external gender experts when preparing the GEP, produced yearly reports on the progress of the GEP with measurable indicators, and has a monitoring committee of the GEP constituted by a negotiation table (comprising the employer's side and the legal representation of the workers). We publish yearly some gender indicators, and in the sustainability report, we include all the equality actions carried out throughout the year.

2 out of 5 organisations that are not required to have the GEP has a GEP in place. In 2 of 5 organisations that do not need to have a GEP, gender disaggregated data about representation was not provided.

Gender mainstreaming

In October and November 2024, the questionnaire on gender mainstreaming was shared among the above-mentioned 5 consortia. The 5 consortia include more than 80 organisations. The online questionnaire was at least clicked on 435 times, the total number of valid responses, which answered

all the questions, was 15. 18 persons answered questions 1 and 2, 16 persons answered questions 1 – 12, 15 persons answered question 1 – 15. 60 % of the respondents were women, 40 % were men.

1. The research / pilots you are involved in:
 - a) focus on a single / very dominant primary environmental benefit – 17 %
 - b) includes the interplay of a few environmental benefits – 6 %
 - c) includes environmental, social and economic benefits – 83 %

2. Do you collect gender-disaggregated data?
 - d) No – 56 %
 - e) Sometimes – 17 %
 - f) Always – 33 %

If you do not collect gender-disaggregated or you do so only sometimes, why is this the case?

Indicators are not dependent on gender

- We do not collect GDG because there are no significant gender-based differences in the scope of our work, making such data unnecessary for our analysis.
- It was never of interest.
- My WP does not collect data.
- The research project revolves around improving wastewater treatment and water reuse. Therefore, only quantitative data is collected.
- Ost collected data are not related to gender. Accessibility to site may be disaggregated but we cannot collect this information as the pilot is a public space.
- Not needed for our work in the project, we lead a transversal work package, not a research work package.
- It is not necessary.
- Indicators are not dependent on gender.

3. Have you at any stage of your work conducted a gender analysis, trying to understand if or how your NBS / tool will affect men and women?
 - g) No – 63 %
 - h) Sometimes – 25 %
 - i) Always – 13 %

If you have not conducted / only sometimes conduct a gender analysis, what could be the reasons for this, in your opinion? Please share a few thoughts bellow.

- Because we have a balanced mix of genders in users.
- We do not collect gender-disaggregated data because there are no significant gender-based differences in the scope of our work, making such data unnecessary for our analysis.
- It has not been required so far.
- We are planning to do this in the future.
- So far it has not been necessary.
- The project aims to achieve an overall solution to environmental problems involving wastewater treatment and water reuse. Thus, the problem is beneficial for society as whole, regardless of gender.
- I primarily look at the degree to which gender can determine perceptions and values around NBS benefits
- I am more focused on technical aspects.
- Not relevant for the type of work we do in the project

4. How often do you consult organisations or experts dealing with gender issues in your work?
- Never – 44 %
 - Sometimes – 38 %
 - Always – 19 %

If the answers were never or sometimes, what is your opinion about your organization's practice and the reasons behind it?

- It is needed because of harassment issues (mainly toward women, of course). it is working well.
- There are a lot of transitory female researchers but just a few of them make part of the stable staff. When stabilized, they most often cover supporting tasks to discharge male stable researchers from no scientific tasks.
- we do not regularly consult organisations or experts on gender issues, as gender-related concerns are not a significant factor in our current projects.
- I think it is a matter of awareness of importance.
- The project aims to achieve an overall solution to environmental problems involving wastewater treatment and water reuse. gender consultants or organizations have not been consulted thus far because the benefits around the project are not exclusively for a gender or other.
- We do not have gender aspects at the forefront, it's oftentimes something we may or may not remember to address.
- Not a requirement for our organisation, we have had discussions about a GEP, currently there are more women employees in the organisation.

5. When you conduct internal or external meetings, do you think about issues such as gender parity, making sure that men and women have the possibility to express their views equally and that all views are taken equally into consideration when making decisions?
- Never – 19 %
 - Sometimes – 6 %
 - Always – 75 %

If the answers were never or sometimes, what could be the reasons for this, in your opinion? Please share a few thoughts bellow.

- man and women are equals. you have the expert of the subject in front of you in that meeting and it doesn't matter if its a man or a woman. all participants should express their views and they all get equal opportunities in our company and in my meetings.
- gender equality in representation is very important, but in some instances, when going for the topic before all, we may end up with only female or predominantly male representation. trying to go 50-50 in all instances can sometimes become artificial.
- when conducting internal or external meetings, we usually do not need to specifically design for gender balance, as the participation of both men and women is already well balanced.

6. Do you think it is important and/or relevant to mainstream gender into your work?
- it is relevant only in very few occasions – 6 %
 - it is overrated – 6 %
 - yes - 88 %

7. Do you think your research / work could in any way pay more attention to the gender dimension?

- a) No – 69 %
 - b) Yes – 31 %
 - economical/social indicators could involve gender aspect.
 - asking different sets of questions to different genders, trying really to understand from each their perspective rather than afterwards assessing whether there is any gender differences in how respondents/participants reply,.
 - we always address gender when our work is related to use of an nbs (but not on its own without other diversity issues.
 - social acceptance/impact of nbs can be assessed in a disaggregated way
8. Do you think that your levels of knowledge are sufficient to deal with gender and social justice in your interventions?
- a) my knowledge is adequate – 60 %
 - b) I don't always know how gender and social justice could be integrated into my work – 20 %
 - c) I would like to know more about it – 20 %
9. Do you have dedicated time to integrate gender and the social dimension into your work?
- a) Always – 40 %
 - b) only sometimes – 47 %
 - c) it is a task that I need to carry out in my free time – 13 %
10. What could be the next steps that would motivate you to further include the gender and social dimension in your considerations (more than one answer is possible)?
- a) dedicated funding – 67 %
 - b) new modus operandi within our entity (more inclusive actions, more attention to social dimension) – 60 %
 - c) more knowledge – 20 %
 - d) evidence that it has impact – 53 %
 - e) any other (please elaborate):